

INSTRUCTING STUDENTS WITH VARIED SKILL LEVELS IN EDUCATIONAL SETTINGS

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Norhojaeva Muborak Murodhojaevna

Senior teacher of Foreign Languages Department, Journalism Mass
Communication University of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

The primary goal of education is not only to provide students with valuable information but also to cultivate their critical thinking skills, decision-making abilities, and mental capacities. Educators should inspire students' curiosity, creativity, and imagination; expand their perspectives; enhance their thinking processes; and enrich their overall knowledge. However, each student possesses unique potential, learning at their own pace and in their own way, influenced by their personality, learning style, or even gender. Such a classroom is referred to as a mixed-ability class. This paper aims to investigate the teaching of mixed-ability students in educational settings.

Keywords: *foreign language, mixed-ability, learning style, effective learners*

Teaching classes with differing skill levels is a fundamental aspect of daily life for many ESL/EFL teachers. These educators often encounter students who possess a wide range of language abilities, requiring them to adapt their instructional methods to meet the diverse needs of each learner. By embracing this challenge, teachers foster an inclusive learning environment that encourages all students to thrive, regardless of their starting point. This approach not only enhances language acquisition but also promotes collaboration and peer learning, as students can support one another in their journeys. Ultimately, teaching mixed-ability classes enriches the educational experience for both teachers and students, highlighting the importance of flexibility and creativity in lesson planning and classroom management. Richards (1998) has asserted that “Every class we ever teach is mixed ability” (p.1). In a similar vein, Rinvoluceri (1986) argues that “ We do not teach a group, but thirty separate people. Because of this, the problem of mixed abilities in the same room seems absolutely natural, and it is the idea of teaching a unitary lesson that seems odd” (p.17). Therefore, one of the roles teachers should seek to develop is creating a more successful methodological approach to their mixed ability class so that they neither leave the struggling students behind nor fail to engage advanced students. As

Casanave (2002) aptly points out, academic writing poses a “clueless” challenge because the rules of the “game” are almost all implicit (p.19).

Mixed ability classes need more attention from teachers. According to Ireson and Hallam (2001), teachers should understand that a class is multi-level. This is because children have different development rates, such as different strengths and weaknesses. Hedge (2000) stated that teaching a mixed-ability classroom is a critical and real issue that educators and teachers face on a regular basis. Although each learner has a distinct method for acquiring English, along with differing levels of language proficiency and learning speeds, there is a general need for teachers to implement strategies that engage all students effectively. Teachers face various challenges when instructing a mixed-ability class, including the differences in understanding, learning styles, motivation, and proficiency levels among their students. Of all these, textual competence (Bachman, 1990), or the ability to develop and organize their ideas in an academically persuasive manner according to “rules of cohesion and rhetorical organization” (Bachman, 1990, p. 88) constitutes the most formidable and crucial challenge. From our personal experience as classroom teachers, we share with Hayashin’s (2005) observation that students’ writings more often than not end up lacking a clear logical flow and unity, not to mention a persuasive linear argument.

Harris and Snow (2004) express concern that the push for improved achievement may have led Modern Languages teachers to feel pressured to create increasingly colorful flashcards or develop more differentiated worksheets. They propose that a more effective alternative would be to concentrate on enabling students to become better learners. They recommend granting students greater ownership not only in selecting the content they engage with but also in determining their learning processes. This approach aligns with the findings of HM Inspectors of Education, which suggest that teaching a mixed-ability class can be effective when all students are given the opportunity to experience success and learn as individuals. By allowing pupils to take charge of their educational journey, teachers can foster a more inclusive and motivating environment that caters to diverse learning styles and paces. This empowerment not only enhances student engagement but also helps build confidence, enabling each learner to reach their full potential in the classroom. It is unrealistic to expect any group of pupils whatever the ability to work through a body of work at exactly the same pace. Two thirds of pupils will be working out of their learning style unless the type of task is varied. Fisher (2001:1) suggests that many children don’t achieve their potential because they are told “to make a journey but they have no map”. Children cannot overcome obstacles to learning if they have not acquired the skills to learn effectively. Therefore, teachers should serve as role

models for learning, guiding students on how to become independent and efficient learners. It is essential for pupils to be taught various learning techniques and how to be resourceful in their educational pursuits. By equipping students with these vital skills, teachers can empower them to navigate challenges more successfully and foster a lifelong love of learning.

Michael J. Lawson and Donald Hoban both stress the importance of helping the students to learn different learning strategies so the students can develop their own study skills that work for them, since all students have their own ways of learning. Allowing students to create their own study guides for tests and assignments can be incredibly beneficial for their learning process. This practice not only encourages students to engage more deeply with the material but also allows them to personalize their study methods based on their unique learning preferences. Moreover, as highlighted by Kelly and Hess, promoting cooperation and collaboration among students is essential. They advocate for teachers to encourage students to support one another, ask classmates for help, and provide feedback on each other’s work. This collaborative approach not only enhances students' understanding of the subject matter but also cultivates a sense of community in the classroom. As students learn to rely on one another, they develop greater accountability for their learning journey. Additionally, providing self-assessment materials can be particularly beneficial for weaker students. These tools enable them to monitor their progress, set goals, and reflect on their understanding, fostering a growth mindset. By integrating these strategies, teachers create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment where all students can thrive and take ownership of their educational experiences.

The objective in changing the term is to eliminate stereotypes that exist currently in any society in regard to those with a mixed ability. Educator Robert Pondiscio has argued that mixed-ability grouping in the classroom creates problems of its own, especially the neglect of higher functioning students. He also points out that "tracking," the practice of grouping students by ability, is routinely used in school sports programs, and questions whether educators are more concerned about athletic achievement than they are about academic achievement.

Regardless of the age or ability level of the students you are teaching, it is essential to foster a learning environment that emphasizes enjoyment, accommodates various learning styles, implements clear classroom management systems, and sets a positive example as a role model. Engaging students through fun activities not only makes learning enjoyable but also enhances retention and understanding. It is important to recognize that learners have different preferences and strengths, so incorporating diverse teaching methods—such as visual aids, hands-on activities, and collaborative projects—can help meet the needs of all students.

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